

INPUT NORMALISATION FOR THE ATLAS ANOMALY DETECTION TRIGGER FOR RUN 3

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AUTHOR(S):

Julia Sophie Troppens

EP-ADT-TR

SUPERVISOR(S):

Stefano Veneziano

PROJECT SPECIFICATION

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In 2025 the ATLAS trigger system will be running its first machine learning-based anomaly detection trigger, which includes both L1 and HLT algorithms. The objective of a 2025 summer project will be to study the first data selected by this trigger, and use these results to inform future searches and trigger improvements looking towards 2026 and the HL-LHC.

ABSTRACT

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In 2025, the first anomaly detection algorithm for the ATLAS Level-1 trigger in Run 3 was implemented using machine learning. This report investigates variations of the algorithm with the focus on input normalisation strategies aiming to identify improvements for the 2026 implementation.

Since the algorithm must operate under strict latency and hardware constraints, the number of operations required for normalisation is highly restricted. This study evaluates four approaches: (i) power-of-two standard deviation scaling (current model), (ii) refined power-of-two standard deviation scaling, (iii) floating-point standard deviation scaling, and (iv) full power-of-two standardisation including mean subtraction.

A particular focus is placed on evaluating the impact of normalisation on model performance for (ii) the refined power-of-two standard deviation scaling and (iv) the full power-of-two standardisation. Both methods are studied using a VAE-GAN trained on 2×10^6 Enhanced Bias and Zero Bias events, allowing a comparison of how these normalisation strategies influence the anomaly detection score and reconstruction loss.

The refined power-of-two standard deviation scaling successfully brings all input features to a comparable scale but still retains a strong dependence of the anomaly detection score on the leading jet p_T . In contrast, the full power-of-two standardisation equalises the contribution of all jet and τ lepton p_T features and incorporates muon information. However, this approach suffers from training instability as the learned rules strongly depend on the random seed. Nonetheless, the more balanced treatment of features appears promising for the development of a more robust algorithm.

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1 INTRODUCTION

At LHC proton bunches collide every 25 ns, producing an enormous amount of collision data. Most of these events are well understood and not of interest for new physics analyses, and it is not feasible to record all events. Therefore, a trigger system is used to filter out interesting events that are stored, while the rest are discarded.

The ATLAS trigger is a two-stage system: the L1 and the HLT. The L1 trigger is implemented in firmware and must operate under strict latency constraints. It reduces the event rate from the collision frequency of 40 MHz to about 100 kHz. This is followed by the software-based HLT, which has more relaxed latency requirements and further reduces the event rate to about 3 kHz for permanent storage.

During Run 3, the L1 trigger incorporates the L1 Topological Processor (L1Topo), which receives input from the L1Calo and L1Muon subsystems. These subsystems identify high-energy objects in the calorimeters and muon detectors and provide information such as particle identification, momentum, and flight direction, as determined by the trigger algorithms. Based on this input, the L1Topo performs fast, topology-based trigger decisions (see [1, 2] for detailed descriptions).

In 2025, a new Anomaly Detection trigger (AD) was introduced into the L1Topo, incorporating machine learning methods. This system is designed to capture complex correlations of various input features that traditional approaches may miss. However, because of the strict timing limitations at L1, the ML models must remain extremely compact.

1.1 Current Status

The current AD algorithm is based on a combination of a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) and a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN). It receives 44 inputs per event:

- p_T, η, φ from
 - 6 leading jets
 - 4 leading τ leptons
 - 4 leading muons
- p_T and φ from missing E_T

The VAE learns to compress the data into a small latent representation of only six values and reconstruct it by reducing a custom MSE loss. The GAN learns to distinguish real from fake, thereby producing more realistic outputs.

The model is trained on approximately 2×10^6 Enhanced Bias and Zero Bias events. This allows it to learn how to encode and decode common events, while failing to accurately reconstruct rare ones. Anomalous events can therefore be distinguished from normal ones by applying a threshold to the reconstruction loss. Due to latency constraints, the Level-1 implementation uses only the encoder, mapping events into the latent space. The anomaly detection score is then calculated directly from the latent variables μ .

$$\text{AD score} = \mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2 + \mu_3^2$$

Unpublished analysis results indicate that the model relies primarily on a limited subset of features, while others are ignored. This behaviour is undesirable, as our goal is to make a topological decision that accounts for the interplay among all features characterising an event. The AD algorithm is being updated for next year to address these issues. The new algorithm

must be completed by December 2025.

Improving AD trigger performance is approached in two ways: by optimising the inputs and refining the model. This project focuses mainly on the former, investigating input normalisation and its impact on the model performance.

2 Visual Analysis of Normalisation Effects on Input Distributions

Bringing input features to a comparable scale is essential for the training and performance of neural networks. When features vary widely in scale, those with larger ranges can dominate the loss function, biasing the model [3]. This leads to unequal feature contributions and suboptimal performance. Normalisation mitigates this by ensuring that all inputs contribute more evenly, enabling the model to capture complex correlations between features more effectively.

2.1 Current Method: Power-of-Two Standard Deviation Scaling

The current input normalisation method is inspired by the standard score approach, which is commonly used in machine learning.

$$z = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma}$$

However, the normalisation must be Level-1 compliant, meaning that computational steps must be minimised. Division by arbitrary numbers is not permitted, with the exception of powers of two, since these operations can be implemented as efficient bit shifts without additional computational cost [4]. Therefore, normalisation is reduced to a division by the closest power of two of the standard deviation σ_{pow2} .

$$z = \frac{x}{\sigma_{pow2}}$$

However, with this normalisation method, the scales of the input distributions for the 44 features still vary considerably — for example, the distribution of the first jet p_T compared to the third muon p_T (see Figure 1).

2.2 Refined Power-of-Two Standard Deviation Scaling

Among the input features are the leading objects of jets, taus, and muons. For objects that are not present in a given event, the corresponding inputs are set to 0. Since it is rare for all of these objects to be produced in a single event, a large fraction of the input features are often zero. The high fraction of zero entries leads to very small standard deviations for some features. This leads to a wide distribution range of muon features and higher leading taus. To address this, a second method calculates the standard deviation σ_{pow2} using only the non-zero entries of each feature. Additionally, a minor inaccuracy in the rounding to the next power of two has been corrected, as described in more detail in the Appendix A.1. These adjustments result in a more consistent scale across all input features (see Figure 2).

Figure 1: Input distributions of the first and sixth jet p_T and the third muon p_T in Monte Carlo events containing two Z bosons. The inputs are normalised by the current power-of-two standard deviation scaling method (see Section 2.1).

Figure 2: Input distributions of the first and sixth jet p_T and the third muon p_T of Zero Bias events. The inputs are normalised by the refined power-of-two standard deviation scaling method (see Section 2.2).

2.3 Float-Precision Standard Deviation Scaling

The third method uses floating-point precision of the standard deviation σ of non-zero entries to investigate the effect of rounding and whether it has a significant impact. This method is intended for study purposes only, as division by arbitrary numbers is not feasible under the Level-1 constraints.

2.4 Power-of-Two Standardisation

In all above normalisation methods the p_T offset is noticeable. Exemplary, the comparison of the first and sixth jet p_T is shown in Appendix 2. Its effects on the model are unclear. The fourth method includes mean μ subtraction as part of the standardisation, in addition to dividing by the standard deviation of non-zero entries σ_{pow2} .

$$z = \frac{x}{\sigma_{pow2}} - \frac{\mu}{\sigma_{pow2}}$$

Dividing the input value x and the mean μ individually is important for the event masking described in Section 3.2, where bit precision plays a critical role. It is not yet clear whether the additional subtraction is feasible in firmware, but if it yields good results, this approach can be investigated further.

3 Evaluating the Impact of Normalisation on Model Performance

In this section, the impact of the normalisation method on the performance of the anomaly detection (AD) algorithm is analysed. In unsupervised learning, model evaluation cannot rely on efficiency metrics, since no ground truth labels are available for the dataset. Instead, the performance of the algorithm is assessed indirectly by visualising and analysing its predictions.

3.1 Float-Precision vs Power-of-Two-Precision

First, the correlation between the AD scores obtained with float precision and power-of-two precision was examined. The two plots on the left in Figure 3 show a moderate correlation between the predictions of the two models trained with different precisions. For comparison, the effect of the random seed is shown on the right, indicating that the impact of precision choice is of a similar order of magnitude.

Figure 3: Correlation of AD score between the same model: trained with float precision and with power-of-two precision (left) and trained with two different random seeds (right).

In the following, the analysis focuses only on the refined power-of-two standard deviation scaling (see Section 2.2) and the power-of-two standardisation (see Section 2.4), as these are the only candidates considered for practical implementation.

3.2 AD Model Alterations for Introducing Offset

The input data contains zero entries for objects that do not exist in an event. Since the AD algorithm should focus on reconstructing existing objects, a mask is applied in the following steps:

- Data and reconstructed data are masked for the calculation of the MSE loss during training and model prediction.
- Data are masked for the autoencoder during encoder and decoder training.
- Reconstructed data are masked when used as input for discriminator training.

In the case of standard deviation scaling, the mask filters out entries that are exactly zero. For full standardisation, which also includes subtracting the feature mean, the mask must instead compare each feature value to its offset. Here, the influence of bit precision becomes relevant. A detailed description of both mask implementations, including their precision settings, is provided in the Appendix A.2.

Figure 4: Correlation of AD score between models with 3 different masks: no mask, the old implementation and a new implementation.

Figure 4 illustrates the effects of the masks on training. The first row corresponds to standard deviation scaling: both the old mask and the new definition with offset = 0 yield

identical results, indicating that the chosen precision boundaries are suitable. The observed deviation from the no-mask case arises from masking the reconstructed data. The second row corresponds to the full standardisation: the first plot shows that the old mask does not filter out any events, whereas the second plot demonstrates that the implementation of a different mask has a visible effect on the training.

3.3 Correlation of Standard Deviation Scaling and Standardisation

Figure 5 compares the correlation between standard deviation scaling and standardisation across four different random seeds. The objective was to determine whether consistent underlying rules could be identified for detecting anomalous events, independent of the chosen normalisation method. However, the resulting correlation plots show that the choice of normalisation is important for the predictions of the model.

Figure 5: Correlation of AD score between two models trained with data normalised with standard deviation scaling and standardisation for four different random seeds.

The offset in the data influences how the reconstruction score is calculated from the latent space. Therefore, a detailed comparison of the respective reconstruction scores is provided in Appendix Section A.3.

3.4 Performance of the Refined Power-of-Two Standard Deviation Scaling

Up to this point, only comparative analyses have been presented, showing that changes to the inputs and the model have an effect on the models predictions. In the following, the report focusses on assessing which of the two normalisation method performs better, using different evaluation metrics introduced in this section.

3.4.1 Feature Distribution of Anomalous Events

To visualize how anomalous events look like, the 10^{-3} fraction of events with the highest AD scores were classified as anomalous. Their feature distributions were then compared against the overall feature distributions in order to highlight what distinguishes anomalous events from the overall data set. Figure 6 presents the p_T distribution of the first leading jet, first leading τ lepton, first leading muon and the missing E_T . The percentage shown in the upper right corner in each plot corresponds to the fraction of events that contain the respective object.

The first plot showing the p_T distribution of the first leading jet indicates that anomalous events always contain at least one jet. The difference in the distributions between the two categories

is striking. Both have distinct peaks, which are well separated from each other. This behaviour is similar to applying a selection cut that classifies events with high- p_T jets as anomalous. For the next leading jets (see Appendix Figure 12), the effect of the cut on p_T transitions into a selection based primarily on the existence of the jet rather than its transverse momentum.

The p_T distribution of the τ leptons, shown in Figure 6 and Appendix Figure 13, follow a similar trend to that observed for the jets. The selection shifts from a bias towards high- p_T values to a criterion based on the existence of the particle. However, in contrast to the jets, the distribution starts with a much broader peak, indicating that while high- p_T τ leptons are favoured, the effect is more of a bias than a strict cut.

Figure 6: p_T distribution of the first leading object of the four feature categories (jets, τ leptons, muons and missing E_T) for anomalous events compared to all events.

The muon distribution shows the same percentage of events containing a muon for overall and anomalous events. Also the shapes of the distributions are matching. The same applies to all higher leading muons. This indicates that the algorithm does not introduce any bias on the individual muon features. Consequently, the only remaining information that can be learned from the muons comes from their correlations with other particles. Otherwise they would be effectively ignored by the model.

The missing E_T distribution shows a broad peak for anomalous events, indicating that high- p_T events are preferred by the anomaly classification. However, lower- p_T events are still included. The algorithm biases towards, but does not exclusively select, high- p_T events.

For all objects, the φ and η distributions show the same behaviour across both event categories. As an example, the two distributions of the leading jet are presented in the Appendix Figure 14. This indicates that no particular flight direction of any particle is classified as anomalous.

3.4.2 p_T Correlation with Anomaly Score

In the previous section feature distributions of anomalous events revealed a direct correlation between the p_T values and the anomaly classification of an event. In the following this correlation is analysed further. All p_T correlation plots with the three latent variables, the anomaly detection (AD) score, and the reconstruction score are provided in the Appendix A.4.2. The AD score shown in the fourth column and the reconstruction loss shown in the fifth column appear broadly similar, suggesting that applying a cut on the AD score provides a good approximation for a Level-1 implementation as discussed in Section 1.1. Since anomalous events in the previous section were defined based on the AD score, the following discussion focuses on the fourth column of the plots.

The strong high- p_T dependence of the first leading jet can be observed in the first row, where the scatter plot reveals a clear correlation. For the higher-order jets, the scatter plots display two overlapping structures: a linearly rising trend that reflects the same correlation between p_T and the AD score, and a vertical band at the minimal p_T value that extends across a wide range of AD scores. This latter structure corresponds to events with lower p_T values, which occur much more frequently. The elevated scores in this region may be driven by other input features or by the combined effect of multiple variables.

The same observation can be made when examining the p_T correlations of the τ leptons. For the muons, both structures are also visible. However, the horizontal band is broader, indicating that a wider p_T range shows no correlation with the AD score.

In the case of the missing E_T , the latent variables are very descriptive. The variable μ_2 shows a clear correlation with p_T , while μ_1 and μ_3 form a box in the scatter plots, indicating no correlation with p_T . Together, this results in a broad p_T range for the anomalous events, with only a slight bias towards higher missing E_T values, leading to the distribution observed in Figure 6.

3.4.3 Random Seed Dependence

Figure 7: Correlation plots of the anomaly detection (AD) score of the same model trained with four different random seeds.

During the training of the encoder model, the weights are ideally optimised to minimise the loss. This implies that, for the same model trained with the same input normalisation, the same global minimum should in principle be reached. However, the correlation plots for four different random seeds reveal certain similarities alongside a considerable degree of randomness

(see Figure 7 for the AD score and Appendix 15 for the reconstruction score). As shown in the previous sections, the classification rules for one seed focus strongly on p_T values of the first leading jet and also higher leading jets and τ leptons, suggesting that this behaviour may also occur for other seeds. The observed similarities may therefore likely be driven by the strong p_T dependence of the leading jets and leading τ leptons.

3.5 Performance of the Power-of-Two Standardisation

In this section, the same analysis steps are repeated, this time looking at the standardisation method. This means, the input data is normalised with full standardisation, including mean subtraction, and the model implementation applies the corresponding mask. Apart from this adjustment, the training remains unchanged. The configuration was originally optimised for the current model and is reused here.

3.5.1 Feature Distribution of Anomalous Events

Figure 8: p_T distribution of the first leading object of the four feature categories (jets, τ leptons, muons and missing E_T) for anomalous events compared to all events.

For this normalisation method as well, the η and φ distributions of anomalous events and of all events are identical. This indicates that a distinction based only on the flight direction of a feature is not made.

The p_T distributions of the first leading jet and first leading τ lepton, shown in Figure 8, are very similar. For anomalous events, the p_T values are spread across a wide range, with a slight enhancement after the overall peak has flattened out. This indicates that the algorithm learns to recognise similar patterns in both objects and exhibits a bias towards higher p_T . However, the effect is less strict than in the case of standard deviation scaling, where the behaviour

corresponds almost to a hard cut on the first leading jet p_T .

For higher leading objects, the p_T distributions of jets and τ leptons also show similar behaviour (see Appendix 16 and 17). The fraction of anomalous events containing the respective object is close to one hundred percent, and the distributions display a broad plateau with a small peak following the peak of the overall events. This suggests that both the leading and higher leading objects are treated and prioritised in a similar way by the algorithm.

The muon distributions of the two event categories, on the other hand, appear broadly similar. But in contrast to standard deviation scaling, the number of anomalous events containing the first muon is slightly higher than in the overall sample. For the second muon, this difference increases up to a factor of two, and for the third muon up to a factor of four. The rare occurrence of muons prevents them from being treated in the same way as the other objects, however, with this normalisation it is evident that these features are taken into account for the anomaly classification.

The missing E_T distribution for anomalous events shows a broad, flat, Gaussian-like shape. This behaviour is comparable to the distribution observed with standard deviation scaling.

3.5.2 p_T Correlation with Anomaly Score

Again in Appendix A.5.2 all p_T correlation plots with the latent variables, the anomaly detection (AD) score, and the reconstruction score are shown. This time, a comparison of the correlation plots of the anomaly detection (AD) score and the reconstruction score, reveals significant deviations. The reconstruction score exhibits a horizontal distribution of scatter points for many features, indicating that anomaly classification is not directly dependent on p_T . This is encouraging, as it suggests that the algorithm may be able to identify rare events independently of high- p_T features. Therefore, it may identify anomalous events which other algorithms overlook. In contrast, the distributions of scatter points for the AD scores resemble more closely those obtained with standard deviation scaling for both the AD and reconstruction scores. This implies that in case of the full standardisation using the AD score as a Level-1 approximation of the reconstruction score is not well suited. Nevertheless, since the algorithm's decisions are based on the AD score, the focus in the following discussion remains on the first four columns of the plots.

The correlation plots with the latent variables show horizontal band structures. Some of these bands have opposite signs, resulting in similar contributions to the AD score. The origin of these bands is not entirely clear, but they may arise from limitations of the small encoder architecture. Due to the mean subtraction, the p_T distribution ranges to minus values and empty events are not zero. Thus, it is more complex to learn from the input features. The newly introduced complexity may be a challenge for the limited model architecture. These band structures are, as a result, also present in the AD score.

In contrast to standard deviation scaling, the AD p_T correlation plots show either a vertical band for low p_T values or a correlated trend, both of which are combined with the horizontal lines described above. Additionally, unlike in the standard deviation scaling case, empty objects—represented by the thin line directly next to the y-axis—exhibit very low AD loss. Consequently, events containing fewer objects are less likely to be classified as anomalous. This hints that this algorithm mainly focuses on the existence of particles in an event for the anomaly classification.

3.5.3 Random Seed Dependence

The plots in Figure 9 visualise whether the model, trained with different random seeds, is able to converge to the same global minimum. The correlation plots of the anomaly detection (AD) score suggest otherwise. In all cases, the scatter points are spread over a square region with horizontal and vertical bands. This indicates that the vertical bands observed in the previous section are not consistent across different seedings and therefore do not have a physical meaning but rather appear to be a model artefact.

Figure 9: Correlation plots of the AD score of the same model trained with four different random seeds.

The correlation plots of the reconstruction score in Figure 10 show that the model predictions diverge more clearly when using the reconstruction score. The analysis from the two previous sections revealed that, with this normalisation method, the model does not emphasize the p_T value of the first leading jet as strongly as in the standard deviation scaling, allowing it to learn more complex decision rules. Nevertheless, the results also reveal variability in predictions across different random seeds, highlighting the instability of the training. With this normalisation, the model is effectively solving a more complex task than before, which affects its training behaviour. Consequently, the optimal training configuration such as learning rate and number of epochs may differ.

Figure 10: Correlation plots of the reconstruction score of the same model trained with four different random seeds.

4 Conclusion

In this project, four different normalisation methods were introduced and their impact on model performance for anomaly detection was analysed. The comparison between standard deviation scaling using floating-point precision and using the next power-of-two was brief and not sufficient to demonstrate that the next power of two can reproduce results comparable to floating-point precision. Given the strict deadline for finalising the algorithm, and the fact that floating-point division is not feasible in practice, the focus was shifted towards studying and optimising the methods that are realistically implementable.

The investigated metrics are not sufficient to fully understand the behaviour of the algorithm, but the power-of-two definition of the model was able to identify consistent rules across different random seeds. This is an indication that a global minimum was reached in other words consistent rules to identify anomalous events. However, the results also show that anomaly classification heavily prioritises the p_T of the leading jet. As a consequence, the seed-independent rule learned by the model is based on a cut on a single feature, while muon features are hardly taken into account. Since L1Topo already provides trigger algorithms that make decisions based on cuts on individual features and particle multiplicities, this strong focus on the leading jet p_T is redundant. The actual goal is to develop an algorithm capable of identifying rules in the data that define anomalous events beyond such simple cuts. How many events are classified as anomalous that would not otherwise have been triggered, and what their characteristics are, has not yet been investigated. Therefore, it is difficult to assess how well the algorithm actually performs. Nevertheless, it is necessary to establish a way to balance the contributions of all features more equally to optimise this trigger algorithm.

The model using the power-of-two standardisation addresses the issue, treating all jet p_T features and τ lepton p_T features equally. And also muons contribute to the anomaly classification. However, this normalisation introduces new complications. Training stability is low, meaning that the learned rules are strongly influenced by random seeding, and no clear rules corresponding to a global minimum are found. The training behaviour is strongly affected by the offset subtraction of the p_T features. The training configuration was optimised for the current model, while this model has to learn more complex rules. Therefore tuning the training duration and learning rate could potentially improve the performance.

Another possible reason for the strong variation is that the chosen architecture is too small to compactly encode all relevant event information in the latent space. This limitation of model size could also affect the standard deviation scaling case, but it is less apparent there due to the strong emphasis on the p_T cut of the first leading jet. To address this issue, the problem could be reduced to fewer input features, or the model could be supported by techniques such as knowledge distillation.

Furthermore, the reconstruction score used for training and the AD score used for event classification lead to different outcomes. The AD score should be redefined based on the latent variables to provide a better approximation so that the algorithm learns and predicts using the same score so that it is able to improve its predictions during training.

A Appendix

A.1 Code Correction for Rounding to next Power-of-Two

The old implementation computed $\log_2()$ and rounded to the nearest integer to get the exponent. This way, 2^{exponent} does not always yield the next power of two. In the corrected version the boundary between rounding up and down is raised from 0.5 to 0.584962500721156.

Listing 1: Fixed normalisation code.

```
def round_to_pow2(X):
    """Round input to the nearest power of 2."""

    exponent = np.floor(np.log2(X)+0.4150374992788439)
    X_pow2 = 2 ** exponent

    return X_pow2
```

A.2 Code Implementation of Mask with Offset

Listing 2: Mask implementation with (mask2) and without (mask1) offset subtraction.

```
mask_1 = tf.keras.backend.cast(
    tf.keras.backend.not_equal(data, 0),
    keras.backend.floatx())

mask_2 = tf.keras.backend.cast(
    ~tf.experimental.numpy.isclose(data, offset, atol=1e-3, rtol=0),
    keras.backend.floatx())
```

The above code shows the implementation of the masks for the standard deviation without offset subtraction and the standardisation with offset subtraction.

Mask 1 returns *true* if the corresponding entry in the data is not equal to zero.

Mask 2 returns *true* if $|a - b| \leq \text{atol} + \text{rtol} \cdot \max(|a|, |b|)$. The parameters that were used are $\text{atol} = 10^{-3}$ and $\text{rtol} = 0$.

A.3 Correlation of Standard Deviation Scaling and Standardisation

Figure 11: Correlation of the reconstruction score between two models trained with data normalised with standard deviation scaling and standardisation for four different random seeds.

A.4 Additional Material for Analysis of the Refined Power-of-Two Standard Deviation Scaling

A.4.1 Anomalous Event Distributions

Figure 12: p_T distribution of the second and third jet for anomalous events compared to all events. The left plot shows that 99% anomalous events contain a second jet, with p_T values remaining high but with a broader peak compared to the first jet. The right plot shows that anomalous events contain a third jet ten times more frequently than all events, while the p_T distribution matches the overall sample. This suggests that the presence of a third jet influences the anomalous classification, while its p_T value is less important.

Figure 13: p_T distribution of second and third τ lepton. The trend is similar to the jet distributions: for higher leading τ s the high p_T peak broadens and the distribution of anomalous events aligns more with the over all distribution. Hence, the existence of a particle influences the anomalous classification more than its p_T value.

Figure 14: η and ϕ distributions of the first jet for anomalous events compared to all events. The similar shapes of the distributions indicate that no preferred flight direction is associated with anomalous classification. These η and ϕ distributions are exemplary for all other particles.

A.4.2 Correlation Plots of p_T and Latent Variables and Loss Scores

A.4.3 Random Seed Dependence

Figure 15: Correlation plots of the anomaly detection (AD) score and the reconstruction score of the same model trained with different random seeds. The inputs are normalised by standard deviation scaling.

A.5 Additional Material for Analysis of Power-of-Two Standardisation

A.5.1 Anomalous Event Distributions

Figure 16: p_T distribution of the second and third jet for anomalous events compared to all events. The left plot shows that 99% anomalous events contain a second jet, with p_T values remaining high but with a broader peak compared to the first jet. The right plot shows that anomalous events contain a third jet ten times more frequently than all events, while the p_T distribution matches the overall sample. This suggests that the presence of a third jet influences the anomalous classification, while its p_T value is less important.

Figure 17: p_T distribution of second and third τ lepton. The trend is similar to the jet distributions: for higher leading τ s the high p_T peak broadens and the distribution of anomalous events aligns more with the over all distribution. Hence, the existence of a particle influences the anomalous classification more than its p_T value.

A.5.2 Correlation Plots of p_T and Latent Variables and Loss Scores

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